

Steric Enhancement of Resonance—Evidence from Ultraviolet Spectral Study on some Halogeno- and Nitro-methoxyacetophenones

M. KRISHNA PILLAY* and S. PALANIVELU

Department of Chemistry, Bharathidasan University, Tiruchirapalli-620 024

Manuscript received 8 January 1986, revised 23 July 1987, accepted 22 August 1987

The uv spectral study on some halogeno- and nitro-methoxyacetophenones furnishes evidence for the phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance. There occurs a red-shift of 1L_a band when a halogen is present in the position *ortho* to the methoxyl group in 4-methoxyacetophenone. The oscillator strength increases from acetophenone to 4-methoxyacetophenone and then to 3-halogeno- and 3-nitro-4-methoxyacetophenones. The spectral data of the above compounds lend support for the concept of steric enhancement of resonance.

SUPPORT for the concept of steric enhancement of resonance (SER) has been furnished by a number of kinetic and spectral studies¹⁻⁵. Kamlet *et al.*⁶⁻¹⁰ while studying the uv spectra of alkyl nitrobenzenes observed a similar phenomenon. In this work we give some more evidence for SER from uv studies on some halogeno- and nitro-methoxyacetophenones.

Experimental

The 3-halogenoacetophenones were prepared by the diazotisation of 3-aminoacetophenone followed by Sandmeyer reaction¹¹. The 3-halogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones were obtained by the diazotisation of *o*-anisidine and subsequent conversion into 2-halogenoanisole by Sandmeyer reaction followed by acetylation¹². 4-Methoxy-3-nitroacetophenone was prepared by the nitration of 4-methoxyacetophenone¹³. 3,5-Dichloro-, 3,5-dibromo- and 3,5-diiodo-4-methoxyacetophenones were prepared by the halogenation of 4-hydroxyacetophenone and subsequent methylation following literature procedure^{14,15}. The uv spectra of the compounds were recorded in methanol (AnalaR) using a Carl-Zeiss Specord UV VIS spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The absorption maxima and intensities of some of the acetophenones are presented in Table 1. Acetophenone shows a weak band around 35 200 cm^{-1} (ϵ_{max} , 2 300) and another high intense band at 41 280 cm^{-1} (ϵ_{max} , 12 500). The low energy band is assigned as 1L_b band and the high energy band as 1L_a band of benzene on Platt's notation¹⁶. The high energy 1L_a band is more susceptible to substitution in the benzene ring.

When a electron-releasing methoxyl group is present in the *para*-position, the high energy 1L_a band undergoes a red-shift, merges with the 1L_b band and appears at 37 000 cm^{-1} (ϵ_{max} , 15 700 ; $\Delta\nu = 4 280$). There occurs a further red-shift when a halogen is present in a position *ortho* to the methoxyl group (Sl. nos. 4, 5 and 6 in Table 1). This observation is in accordance with the phenomenon of SER. The absorption maximum of 4-methoxy-3-nitroacetophenone occurs at 39 200 cm^{-1} (Sl. no. 7, Table 1). Contrary to the expectation of a red-shift, a significant blue-shift is noticed in this compound, but the intensity of absorption has been considerably increased. When there are two halogen atoms in the *o,o'*-positions with respect to the methoxyl group, the absorption maximum is shifted towards the higher energy region as it is seen in the spectra of compounds of Sl. nos. 8, 9 and 10 (Table 1). The conventional phenomenon of steric inhibition of resonance operates here.

TABLE 1—UV ABSORPTION SPECTRAL DATA AND OSCILLATOR STRENGTH OF SOME HALOGENO- AND NITRO-ACETOPHENONES IN METHANOL

Sl. no.	Acetophenones	$\bar{\nu}_{\text{max}}$ cm^{-1}	ϵ_{max}	$\Delta\bar{\nu}_{112}$ cm^{-1}	<i>f</i>
1.	Acetophenone	41 280	12 500	8 640	0.248
2.	4-Methoxy-	37 000	15 700	11 200	0.404
3.	3-Fluoro-4-methoxy-	37 340	16 300	6 240	0.468
4.	3-Chloro-4-methoxy-	36 600	18 600	6 720	0.574
5.	3-Bromo-4-methoxy-	36 740	18 900	4 800	0.417
6.	3-Iodo-4-methoxy-	36 560	15 900	5 120	0.375
7.	4-Methoxy-3-nitro-	39 200	18 900	8 000	0.696
8.	3,5-Dichloro-4-methoxy-	39 200	10 100	4 460	0.208
9.	3,5-Dibromo-4-methoxy-	38 880	11 600	4 480	0.239
10.	3,5-Diiodo-4-methoxy-	38 000	9 400	4 480	0.194
11.	3-Fluoro-	41 500	8 900	—	—
12.	3-Chloro-	41 480	9 500	—	—
13.	3-Bromo-	40 680	6 900	—	—
14.	3-Iodo-	40 680	7 900	—	—
15.	3-Nitro-	37 700	6 300	—	—

Analysis of oscillator strength: In conjugated systems the shift in $\lambda_{\max}$ ($\Delta\lambda$) as well as changes in $\epsilon_{\max}$ may be chosen as factors to explain the spectral behaviour of the compounds. The changes in the intensities of absorption maxima of the above anisoles are analysed in terms of oscillator strength. Any increase in the mesomeric effect or enhanced resonance will give rise to increased transition probability which is measured in terms of the oscillator strength (f) given by the equation,

$$f = 4.6 \times 10^{-9} \times \epsilon_{\max} \times \Delta\bar{\nu}_{1/2}$$

where, $\Delta\bar{\nu}_{1/2}$ is half-band integrated intensity. For the unsymmetrical bands (e.g. 3,5-dihalogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones) the oscillator strength was computed as suggested by Jaffe and Orchin¹⁷. For highly allowed transition f tends to 1. The oscillator strengths of nitro- and halogeno-acetophenones calculated using this expression are presented in Table 1. The value of oscillator strength increases from 0.248 to 0.404 when we go from acetophenone to 4-methoxyacetophenone. The crossed conjugation increases when a methoxyl group is introduced in the 4-position of acetophenone. For 3-fluoro-4-methoxy-, 3-chloro-4-methoxy- and 3-bromo-4-methoxy-acetophenones there is a further increase in the oscillator strength barring the iodo compound showing that when a halogen atom is introduced *ortho* to the methoxyl group the resonance interaction between the methoxyl and acetyl groups increases. This observation is in conformity with the concept of SER.

The oscillator strengths of 3,5-dihalogeno-4-methoxyacetophenones are lower than that of 4-methoxyacetophenone due to steric inhibition of resonance. The oscillator strength of 4-methoxy-3-nitroacetophenone is 0.696, whereas those of 4-methoxyacetophenone and acetophenone are 0.404

and 0.248, respectively (Table 1). This reveals that there is more conjugation between methoxyl and acetyl functions in 4-methoxy-3-nitroacetophenone than in 4-methoxyacetophenone. Though the uv data of this compound do not furnish evidence for steric enhancement of resonance the oscillator strength study does.

References

1. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1960, 25, 21.
2. V. BALIAH and V. M. KANAGASABAPATHY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 182.
3. V. BALIAH and P. V. V. SATYANARAYANA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 883.
4. K. GANAPATHY and M. RAMANUJAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 958.
5. K. GANAPATHY, M. RAMANUJAM, T. BALASUBRAMANIA, M. K. PILLAY and S. PALANIVELU, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 689.
6. M. J. KAMLET, J. C. HOFFSOMMER and H. G. ADOLPH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 8925.
7. M. J. KAMLET, H. G. ADOLPH and J. C. HOFFSOMMER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 4018.
8. M. J. KAMLET, H. G. ADOLPH and B. JOHNSON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, 30, 2864.
9. M. J. KAMLET, J. C. HOFFSOMMER, R. R. MINESINGER and H. G. ADOLPH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 3070.
10. M. J. KAMLET and R. R. MINESINGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 91, 4155.
11. J. C. E. SIMPSON, C. M. ATKINSON, K. SCHOFIELD and D. STEPHENSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 646.
12. J. ENGLISH, JR., J. F. MEAD and C. NIEMANN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 350.
13. H. OELSCLAGER, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1957, 290, 587 (*Chem. Abst.*, 1958, 52, 8989).
14. H. M. PRIESTLY and E. MONESS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 355.
15. SCHERING-KAHLBAUM A -G., Fr. Pat 809 426/1936 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1937, 31, 262016).
16. J. R. PLATT *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 484.
17. H. H. JAFFE and M. ORCHIN, "Theory and Applications of Ultraviolet Spectroscopy", Wiley, New York, 1962, p. 111.